

CYBERLENINKA

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Madrimova Sh.I.

SURROGAT ONALIK QANCHALIK TO'G'RI TANLOV?

DRJI

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WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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zenodo

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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